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***Abstract.** The purpose of this paper is to involve students in the learning process by using interactive methods. Improve learner's pronunciation skills, through modern technologies and interactive activities. Moreover, this article provides information about interactive techniques such as role-playing, phonetic games and tongue twisters, and describes in detail their application and benefits. By integrating these approaches into the classroom, teachers can create an environment that promotes active participation and increase learner's pronunciation skills.*

***Keywords.** Pronunciation Teaching, Interactive Methods, Phonetic Games, Active Learning, Modern Technologies.*

Introduction. Nowadays, the number of students who are interested in learning English has increased. English consists of several essential skills that learners need to master, and one of the most important aspects of any language is its pronunciation. Effective pronunciation is a cornerstone of clear and confident communication. However, teaching pronunciation has challenges, such as learners often struggle with unfamiliar sounds, intonation, word stress and rhythm. Traditional teaching methods are helpful but can sometimes be boring or not very effective. Interactive approaches, such as role-playing phonetic games, and tongue twisters, actively involve students in the learning process, making it enjoyable and effective. Meanwhile, advancements in technology, including language-learning apps, AI-powered pronunciation tools, and virtual reality simulations, offer personalized feedback and immersive practice opportunities. Together, these methods improve pronunciation skills and there are also increase their confidence in real-life communication. After all, the goal of study is for each student to figure

out the phonetic topic and take an active part in activities during lesson. The teacher's goal is to engage students in the learning process, motivate them, help, and give advice if students have questions according to the pronunciation.

Main text

Pronunciation is a key component of effective communication in any language. Without proper pronunciation, even a good vocabulary and strong grammar may not be clear. Mispronounced words can cause confusion or make communication hard. Therefore, teachers should pay special attention to students' pronunciation, try to make the lesson interesting by using interactive methods and modern technologies. Many kinds of technology can be of value for pronunciation learning and teaching, both those which are specifically designed to work on pronunciation and those not so designed but which have been creatively applied to pronunciation. Interactive methods make pronunciation learning more engaging and effective. Using pronunciation learning approach and designs combined with interactive media, will enable students to learn the material themselves, and learn their own techniques for independent learning. Role-playing activities allow learners to practice real-life conversations helping them focus on stress, rhythm and intonation. These activities help students figure out how work in group. Educators use role-playing techniques to teach social skills [Sr.Sundari:14/2017]. For example, simulating scenarios like asking for directions or ordering food at a restaurant. It helps students pronounce words correctly. Teachers can use apps like Duolingo or Rosetta Stone to practice specific phrases. In tongue twister activity students practice pronouncing difficult sounds, such as "She sells seashells", trying to say them faster and clearer. Simplified tongue twisters make pronunciation practice entertaining and memorable. Young learners often respond positively to these activities, as they tap into their natural inclination for music and language play [Shermamatova S,K. D./2024/296]. Teachers can use Google Speech-to-Text or Voice Thread tools to record students voice and get feedback on their pronunciation. Moreover, Classroom activities should cater to what their students consider their most important personal goals or reasons for learning the language

[Andri Purwanto:83/2019]. Teachers should consider all characteristics of students, the previous experience of relationship and interaction in group, the level of communication culture, the level of intellectual development of students. In other words, all of these aspects affect the success of speech interaction.

In conclusion, effective pronunciation instruction is essential for clear communication in any language. By utilizing interactive methods, such as role-playing, phonetic games, and tongue twisters, teachers can make pronunciation practice engaging and impactful. The integration of modern technologies, such as language learning apps and speech recognition tools, further enhances the learning experience, allowing students to receive immediate feedback and improve their skills. Additionally, understanding the diverse characteristics and backgrounds of students ensures that lessons are tailored to their specific needs, fostering a more effective and supportive learning environment.

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